

PP-2 : SERVING THE UNDERSERVED: A TEAM-BASED OUTREACH MODEL FOR DELIVERING HOME CARE IN A MARGINALISED COMMUNITY

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BACKGROUND:

- Access to healthcare remains a significant challenge for individuals living in underserved and marginalised communities, such as urban slums.
- Social exclusion, poverty, and limited health literacy often contribute to poor health-seeking behaviours and interrupted care.
- In such contexts, effective healthcare delivery requires not only individual effort but coordinated action from the primary healthcare team.

CASE DESCRIPTION:

- Ms. AB, is a 62-year-old woman diagnosed with schizophrenia, on treatment for the past 20 years.
- She also receives ongoing care for diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and drug-induced parkinsonism, with scheduled follow-up at a divisional hospital medical clinic every two months.
- She resides in Maligawatta area with her only living relative — an unmarried sister who is also the principal caregiver, but lacks a stable income. (Figure 1)
- During routine clinic visits, the medical officer noted that the patient herself was absent, with her sister collecting medications on her behalf. (Figure 2)
- Further inquiry revealed that the patient had become bedbound due to advanced parkinsonism and was unable to attend clinic appointments.
- Recognising the need for continuity of care, the head of the institution arranged community-based care delivery via the Public Health Nursing Officer (PHNO). She was accompanied by a healthcare assistant familiar with the area to ensure her personal safety during field visits.
- Despite challenges in her social and environmental context (Figure 3), the patient continues to receive consistent home-based care, helping her maintain optimal control of chronic conditions. With support from the PHNO, her caregiver was trained in essential aspects of care. A trusting relationship with the healthcare team has sustained this patient-centred approach.

Figure 1: Ms. AB and her sister during a home visit by PHNO

Figure 2: Ms. AB's Clinic Record depicting 'PNS – Patient Not Seen'

Figure 3: The challenging environment where Ms. AB lives

CONCLUSION:

- This case demonstrates a meaningful example of **team-based, equity-driven, community care** in a highly underserved setting and offers a practical model for delivering community-based care in marginalised settings.